

CLEVERFOOD Peer-Learning Programme

The CLEVERFOOD peer-learning programme is addressed to **food policy labs** and **food policy councils**. These initiatives involve active stakeholder participation and operate within specific territories (cities, metropolitan areas, and city-regions), contributing to innovation and policymaking. They are implemented by cities, local authorities, and/or other entities (NGOs, universities, etc.) and are policy-oriented, contributing to the development of food system governance strategies and policies at the city-region or national level.

The programme will be organised around learning clusters which will include demonstrators and fellows. It will be open to:

- **20 Demonstrators:** A demonstrator is an entity with direct experience or specific expertise on a subject and is willing to share their experiences and lessons learned.
- **40 Fellows:** A fellow is an entity that wants to learn from an experienced peer and is interested in applying what they have learned in their context.

Participating as a Demonstrator:

Demonstrators will have the chance to share their experience, give visibility to their initiatives and activities, meet other peers, and exchange ideas. Additionally, they will have the opportunity to play a double role and participate in the peer-learning programme as a fellow, allowing them to participate in the activities of another learning cluster as a fellow and visit another demonstrator to learn from their experience.

Participating as a Fellow:

Fellows will have the chance to expand their network and learn from an experienced peer by engaging in online exchanges and in-person visits to the demonstrator's locality. Fellows will be provided with the tools to develop an action plan at the end of the learning process. The best 15 action plans will receive seed funding to implement their action plans.

The advantages of participating in the peer-learning programme:

This peer-learning programme is designed not as a one-way process, but as a reciprocal exchange between peers on how to overcome similar challenges to drive food system transformation. Participants will benefit from Eurocities' expertise in organising peer-learning programmes for cities and local initiatives, as well as in developing learning materials and tools for knowledge-sharing and the development of targeted actions at the local level. The collaboration will extend to the activities of the FOOD 2030 Connected Lab Network.

Methodology:

The peer-learning programme will last approximately three months and include online preparatory meetings, in-person exchanges, and an online follow-up meeting. The preparatory meetings will help identify the participants' learning needs and the focus of the in-person visit, which will last two days and take place in the demonstrator's

locality, combining discussions, meetings with local stakeholders, and field visits. The follow-up meeting will be key to reviewing the lessons learned and identifying the next steps for implementing specific activities aimed at promoting the transition toward sustainable food systems.

Costs and seed funding:

The demonstrators will present their activities and organise a visit to their locality. The programme includes a financial contribution to cover the organisational costs of the visit. The fellows will attend the online meetings, share their learning needs, and travel to the demonstrator's locality. They will receive a reimbursement for their travel and accommodation costs. At the end of the learning process, they will draft an action plan and have the possibility to receive seed funding (€ 5,000) to implement the activities of the action plan.

Application process:

Participants are recruited through two open calls. The First Call for Participants aims to recruit 20 demonstrators (who will also have the possibility to participate in the programme as fellows). The Second Call for Participants will recruit 40 fellows. Eurocities will evaluate the applications and match demonstrators and fellows to form learning clusters based on matching expertise, learning needs, and other factors such as geographical location. These learning clusters are expected to start the collaboration by the end of 2024 and conclude it by the end of 2025.

Timeline:

When	Activity
February 2024	Launch of the First Call for Participants
21 June 2024	Deadline for the First Call for Participants
June 2024	Outcomes of the selection are communicated to the applicants to the First Call for Participants
July 2024	Launch of the Second Call for Participants
August 2024	Deadline of the call for the Second Call for Participants
September 2024	Outcomes of the selection are communicated to the applicants to the Second Call for Participants
September 2024	Learning clusters are formed by Eurocities
October 2024	Info sessions are organised to present the programme
Starting from November 2024	The collaborations start
November 2024-October 2025	20 in-person visits take place in the demonstrators' localities
By November 2025	Eurocities collects all the action plans finalised by the fellows
Beginning of 2026	15 action plans are selected to receive the seed funding